

on various fabrics are given in table 2. With compounds numbering 17, 18, 19, (containing -COOH group), and 20 (containing -SO₃H group) the shades on the fabrics have been found much lighter. The dyed fabrics were tested for their light fastness in Atlas Colour-Fade-Ometer following standard procedures (temp., 110°F; R.H., 32-40%; intensity, 1.4 times mid-summer noon at Kanpur). Fading of the dyed wool, silk, and acetate silk fabrics were classed 5 to 6 standard, and dyed terylene and nylon 4 to 5 standard.

The fungicidal properties of pyrazolone dyes were tested on *Aspergillus niger* using Czapek medium and following dilution technique¹. The growth of fungus was examined under a microscope after 24 hrs and the amounts of the compounds in millimoles which showed complete inhibition are given in column 8, table 1.

The chromatograms of the pyrazolones as well as those of ethyl α -substituted phenylazo acetoacetate dyes were obtained using Whatman no. 1 filter papers, employing descending techniques by wooden chromatographic chambers (temp., 20° ± 1°; eluents, (1) 80% EtOH, and (2) BuOH: AcOH: H₂O :: 8:2:5). The R_f values are recorded in columns 6 and 7 of Table 1.

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Reference

- (Miss) K. SRIVASTAVA and J. K. MEHROTRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 32, 116.

Potential Antimycobacterial Agents.

I. Synthesis of N-Benzylidenediphenylamine-2 carboxylic acid hydrazides

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SINCE the advent of isonicotinic acid hydrazide (INH) as a clinically effective antitubercular drug, a large number of hydrazides have been synthesised and tested for antibacterial properties¹⁻⁸. Isoxazolecarboxylic acid hydrazides have been reported as antileprotic agents⁹ and anticonvulsant activity has been described in phenothiazinecarboxylic acid hydrazides¹⁰. Hydrazones obtained from hydrazides frequently act as monoamine oxidase (MAO) inhibitors¹¹⁻¹³. Besides, hydrazides have been associated with anthelmintic¹⁴ and antifungal¹⁵ activity. In view of these observations it was felt interesting to synthesise a series of N-benzylidenehydrazides (Scheme 1) for biological screening.

SCHEME I

NOTES

Biological Data :

Compounds listed in Table I have been evaluated for their inhibitory effects against four organisms :

TABLE 1—DIPHENYLAMINE-2-CARBOXYLIC ACID HYDRAZIDES (III)

Sl.No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula	Analysis N%	
					Calc.	Found
1.	H ^a	120	53	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₃ O	18.50	18.41
2.	2-CH ₃	129-130	57	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₃ O	17.42	17.65
3.	3-CH ₃	125-127	61	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₃ O	17.42	17.40
4.	4-CH ₃	122	49	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₃ O	17.42	16.98

a, Lit.²¹ m.p. 121.

Escherichia coli, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi* and *Aerobacter aerogenes* by agar diffusion technique¹⁶. Compound nos. 2-5, 8, 12-15, 17, 20-23, 25, 28 and 31 have inhibited the growth of *E. coli*. Ten compounds (1, 5, 9, 11, 13, 14, 19, 21-23) showed inhibition against *S. typhi*. Inhibition against *S. aureus* was observed in two compounds (9, 19). None of the compounds were effective against *A. aerogenes*. Bacterial cultures maintained at C.D.R.I., Lucknow were used.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are not corrected. Infrared spectra (compound nos. 1, 16, 23) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 Spectrophotometer in KBr and were as expected.

TABLE 2—N-BENZYLIDENEDIPHENYLAMINE-2-CARBOXYLIC ACID HYDRAZIDES(IV)

Sl.No.	R	Ar	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol.formula	Analysis %	
						Calc.	Found
1.	2-CH ₃ ^a	Ph	203	57	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₃ O	C, 76.80 H, 5.70 N, 12.76	76.40 5.60 12.82
2.	3-CH ₃ ^a	Ph	163	63	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₃ O	C, 76.80 H, 5.70 N, 12.76	77.10 5.31 12.91
3.	4-CH ₃ ^c	Ph	170	60	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₃ O	N, 12.76	12.95
4.	H ^a	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	222 d	73	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₃	N, 15.55	15.09
5.	2-CH ₃ ^a	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	240 d	70	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃	N, 15.05	14.71
6.	3-CH ₃ ^a	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	232	78	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃	N, 15.05	15.00
7.	4-CH ₃ ^a	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	212 d	69	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃	N, 15.05	14.83
8.	H ^b	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	180-181	72	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₃	N, 15.55	15.61
9.	2-CH ₃ ^c	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	183	65	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃	C, 67.74 H, 4.84 N, 15.05	67.71 4.84 15.03
10.	3-CH ₃ ^c	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	201	65	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃	N, 15.05	14.93
11.	4-CH ₃ ^a	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	218-219	69	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃	N, 15.05	15.10
12.	H ^a	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	199	74	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂	C, 73.04 H, 5.50 N, 12.18	73.00 5.61 12.18
13.	2-CH ₃ ^a	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	204	75	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₂	N, 11.71	11.74
14.	3-CH ₃ ^a	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	189	70	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₂	N, 11.71	11.74
15.	4-CH ₃ ^c	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	195	73	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₂	N, 11.71	12.05
16.	H ^a	2-furyl	188	71	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₂	C, 70.81 H, 4.91 N, 13.77	70.55 5.05 13.51
17.	2-CH ₃ ^a	2-furyl	215	65	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂	N, 12.16	12.01
18.	3-CH ₃ ^b	2-furyl	160	80	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂	N, 12.16	12.02
19.	4-CH ₃ ^b	2-furyl	184	72	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂	C, 71.47 H, 5.33 N, 12.16	71.50 5.20 12.01
20.	H ^b	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	180	70	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ BrN ₃ O	C, 60.91 H, 4.06 N, 10.66	61.25 4.46 10.72
21.	2-CH ₃ ^b	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	200	59	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ BrN ₃ O	N, 10.29	10.59
22.	3-CH ₃ ^b	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	200	68	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ BrN ₃ O	N, 10.29	9.96
23.	4-CH ₃ ^c	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	196-197	60	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ BrN ₃ O	C, 61.76 H, 4.41 N, 10.29	61.40 4.60 10.05
24.	3-CH ₃ ^b	4-N(CH ₃)C ₆ H ₄	198	62	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ N ₄ O	N, 15.05	15.46
25.	4-CH ₃ ^b	4-N(CH ₃)C ₆ H ₄	216-217	66	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ N ₄ O	N, 15.05	15.09
26.	H ^c	3-ClC ₆ H ₄	196-197	70	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ ClN ₃ O	C, 68.66 H, 4.57 N, 12.02	69.01 4.13 11.85
27.	2-CH ₃ ^c	3-ClC ₆ H ₄	208	73	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ ClN ₃ O	N, 11.55	11.56
28.	3-CH ₃ ^a	3-ClC ₆ H ₄	203	80	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ ClN ₃ O	N, 11.55	11.57
29.	4-CH ₃ ^c	3-ClC ₆ H ₄	183-185	63	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ ClN ₃ O	N, 11.55	11.38
30.	H ^b	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	180-182	54	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O	C, 68.66 H, 4.47 N, 12.02	68.31 4.35 12.00
31.	3-CH ₃ ^b	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	187	78	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ ClN ₃ O	N, 11.55	11.68

Recrystallised from a, ethanol; b, acetone; c, aq. acetone.

Diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acids (I) (R = H, 2-CH₃, 3-CH₃, 4-CH₃) were obtained according to the published procedure¹⁷⁻²⁰.

Diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid hydrazides (III, Table 1):

An intimate mixture of diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid (20.0 g.), thionyl chloride (20.0 ml) and absolute methanol (250 ml) was refluxed for 12-15 hrs. Thereafter excess of methanol was distilled off. The contents of the flask were cooled, diluted with 250 ml of water and neutralised with sodium carbonate at 5°-10°. The crude ester thus obtained was filtered and used without further purification.

Hydrazine hydrate 95% (0.2 mole), II (0.1 mole) and 50 ml of methanol were taken in a 500 ml round bottomed flask. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 12 hrs. Excess of methanol was removed in vacuum and the crude hydrazide was recrystallised from ethanol or dilute ethanol.

N-Benzylidenediphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid hydrazides (IV, Table 2):

Equimolar amounts of hydrazide (III) and a suitable aldehyde were suspended in 20 ml of ethanol. The reaction mixture was heated on a steam bath for 1 hr. The crude product thus separated was recrystallised from a suitable solvent.

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References

1. T. RINDERSPACHER and B. PRIJS, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1958, 41, 22.
2. A. WINTERSTEIN, B. HEGEDUS, B. FUST, E. BOHNI and A. STUDER, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1956, 39, 229.
3. W. WERNER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1953, 18, 1333.
4. A. L. MINDZHOYAN, *Arm. Khim. Zh.*, 1966, 19, 793; *Chem. Abs.*, 1967, 67, 539432.
5. O. ISLER, H. GUTMANN, O. STRAUB, B. FUST, E. BOHNI and A. STUDER, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1955, 38, 1033, 1046.
6. K. U. M. PRASAD, B. H. IYER and M. SIRSI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 43, 784.
7. S. S. PARMAR and R. KUMAR, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1968, 11, 635.
8. V. S. MISRA and R. S. VARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 39, 763.
9. T. S. GARDENER, E. WENIS and J. LEE, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 26, 1514.
10. SWISS, 419,136, 1967, *Chem. Abs.*, 1968, 68, 29709c.

11. A. ALEMANY, M. BERNABÉ, E. F. ALVAREZ, M. LOBATA-MAYO and O. NIETO, *Bull. Soc. Chim. (France)*, 1967, 780.
12. D. LIEBERMANN and J.-c. RENIS, *Bull. Soc. Chim. (France)*, 1961, 1952.
13. M. H. WEINSWIG and E. B. ROCHE, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1965, 54, 1216.
14. R. CAVIER and R. RIPS, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1965, 8, 706.
15. BRIT. 1,085,474, 1967; *Chem. Abs.*, 1968, 68, 95567f.
16. R. S. VARMA and S. A. IMAM, *Indian J. Microbiol.*, 1973, 13, 45.
17. A. T. VOGEL, "Practical Organic Chemistry", Third Edition, Longman Group Ltd., London, 1971, p. 991.
18. K. LEHMSTEDT, W. BURNS and H. KLEE, *Ber.*, 1936, 69B, 2399.
19. K. LEHMSTEDT and SCHRADER, *Ber.*, 1937, 70, 838.
20. ULLMANN and BADER, *Ann.*, 1907, 355, 323.
21. A. ALBERT, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 1225.

Use of *p*-Dimethyl Amino Anil of Anthracene Glyoxal as Gravimetric Reagent in the Determination of Platinum and Palladium

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IN our previous communication¹ *p*-dimethyl amino anil of 3-phenanthryl glyoxal was used as gravimetric reagent for platinum in acetonic medium. *P*-dimethyl amino anil of anthracene glyoxal² has been found a good complexing reagent for large number of transition metals². During the complexometric investigations, it has been observed that reagent reacts quantitatively with Pt(IV) and Pd(II) in acetone. Gravimetric estimations of Pt(IV) and Pd(II) with the reagent and effect of various compounds has been thought worthwhile from analytical view point.

Preparation of the solution: Reagent was dissolved in doubly distilled acetone to prepare approximately 0.01M solution. Stock solutions of metal chlorides (J.M.) were prepared in acetone and were standardised gravimetrically³.

Precipitating reagent was slowly added, with constant stirring, to the known volume (05-50 ml) of metal chloride which was prediluted to 25-100 ml. After allowing to stand for 15-20 mins, precipitate was filtered through sintered glass crucible; washed 2-3 times with dry acetone and ether successively; dried in oven and was weighed as Pt(C₂₄H₂₀N₂O)₂Cl₄.